

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

***BULLETIN OF* FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

2025, №6 (20)

МИНИСТЕРСТВО ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ
РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН

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AND CLINIC MEDICINE**
**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА КЛИНИК
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**ВЕСТНИК ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ И
КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

Научный журнал по фундаментальным и клиническим
проблемам медицины
основан в 2022 году

Бухарским государственным медицинским институтом
имени Абу Али ибн Сино
выходит один раз в 2 месяца

Главный редактор – Ш.Ж. ТЕШАЕВ

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2025, № 6 (20)

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О журнале

Журнал зарегистрирован
в Управлении печати и информации
Бухарской области
№ 1640 от 28 мая 2022 года.

Журнал внесен в список
утвержденный приказом № 370/б
от 8 мая 2025 года реестром ВАК
в раздел медицинских наук.

Отпечатано в типографии ООО
“Шарк-Бухоро”. г. Бухара,
ул. Ўзбекистон Муस्ताкиллиги, 70/2.

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CLINICAL USEFULNESS OF PROCALCITONIN IN ANTIBIOTIC DECISION-MAKING DURING SARS-COV-2 INFECTION

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Resume. *Tablee presents laboratory characteristics, as well as potential biomarkers for predicting disease severity in patients infected with SARS-CoV-2. Examined 120 patients with a new coronavirus infection were examined. All patients were laboratory-confirmed to have SARS-CoV-2 infection. Patients were divided into severe cases (n=60) and moderate cases (n=60). The median age was 53 years, 120 patients and 96 (8.0%) of the 120 patients were male. The significance of procalcitonin as a biomarker for assessing the risk of bacterial infection, disease progression, timely administration of antibacterial drugs, and duration of the course of antibacterial therapy was studied.*

Key words: SARS-CoV-2, COVID-19, gastrointestinal, neurological, skin manifestations, procalcitonin.

SARS-COV-2 ИНФЕКЦИЯСИДА АНТИБИОТИКЛАРНИ ТАЙИНЛАШ БЎЙИЧА ҚАРОР ҚАБУЛ ҚИЛИШДА ПРОКАЛЬЦИТОНИННИНГ КЛИНИК АҲАМИЯТИ

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Резюме. *Мақолада SARS-CoV-2 билан инфицирланган беморларда касаллик оғирлигини башорат қилиш учун лаборатор кўрсаткичлар ҳамда эҳтимоллий биомаркерлар келтирилган. Янги корона-вирус инфекцияси билан касалланган 120 нафар бемор текширилди. Барча беморларда SARS-CoV-2 инфекцияси лаборатор усуллар орқали тасдиқланган. Беморлар касалликнинг оғир кечиши (n=60) ва ўртача оғир кечиши (n=60) гуруҳларига ажратилди. Беморларнинг медиан ёши 53 ёшни ташкил этди. 120 нафар беморнинг 96 нафари (80,0%) эркалар эди. Бактериал инфекция хавфини баҳолаш, касаллик прогрессиясини аниқлаш, антибактериал препаратларни ўз вақтида тайинлаш ҳамда антибактериал терапия давомийлигини белгилашда прокальцитониннинг биомаркер сифатидаги аҳамияти ўрганилди.*

Калит сўзлар: SARS-CoV-2, COVID-19, ошқозон-ичак, неврологик, тери намоён бўлишлари, прокальцитонин.

КЛИНИЧЕСКАЯ ЗНАЧИМОСТЬ ПРОКАЛЬЦИТОНИНА ПРИ ПРИНЯТИИ РЕШЕНИЙ О НАЗНАЧЕНИИ АНТИБИОТИКОВ У ПАЦИЕНТОВ С SARS-COV-2

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Резюме. *В таблице представлены лабораторные характеристики, а также потенциальные биомаркеры для прогнозирования тяжести заболевания у пациентов, инфицированных SARS-CoV-2. Было обследовано 120 пациентов с новой коронавирусной инфекцией. У всех пациентов инфекция SARS-CoV-2 была подтверждена лабораторно. Пациенты были разделены на группы с тяжёлым (n=60) и среднетяжёлым (n=60) течением заболевания. Медианный возраст составил 53 года. Из 120 пациентов 96 (80,0%) были мужчинами. Изучена значимость прокальцитонина как биомаркера для оценки риска бактериальной инфекции, прогрессирования заболевания, своевременного назначения антибактериальных препаратов и продолжительности курса антибактериальной терапии.*

Ключевые слова: SARS-CoV-2, COVID-19, желудочно-кишечные, неврологические, кожные проявления, прокальцитонин.

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Introduction. Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), caused by the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), has had a strong impact on health systems around the world [1,2]. Patients with severe pneumonia have a high mortality rate due to the large number of complications they face [3].

It is reported, that in COVID-19, the prevalence of community-acquired bacterial respiratory coinfections (hereinafter referred to as bacterial coinfection) during hospitalization is less than 5% [4,5,6,7]. Although the impact of this complication on mortality is still widely debated, almost three-quarters of patients with COVID-19 receive antibiotics, so the number of prescriptions significantly exceeds the estimated prevalence of bacterial co-infection [8]. Excluding bacterial co-infection at hospital admission in these patients may potentially limit overuse of antibiotics and thus reduce hospital admission costs, potential side effects, and the development of multidrug-resistant infections [9]. PCT is a serum biomarker that has shown promising results in distinguishing between viral and bacterial infections [10, 11, 26], and it is commonly used in conjunction with clinical data as a guideline for de-escalation with prescribing of antibiotics in critically ill patients [12, 13, 14]. The role of PCT in community-acquired pneumonia (CAP) has been evaluated in several studies, but There is no scientific consensus on its usefulness for the diagnosis or administration of antibiotics [15,27]. C-reactive protein (CRP), another well-known systemic marker of inflammation and tissue damage, is widely used by clinicians to monitor infections [16,22]. In patients with COVID-19, CRP at admission correlated with disease severity and was generally a good predictor of an adverse outcome [16,17].

An increase in PCT indicates the addition of a bacterial infection and correlates with the severity of the course, the prevalence of inflammatory infiltration, and the prognosis of the progression of bacterial complications.

Accumulating data indicate that more than 80% of patients with COVID-19 are treated with antibiotics, as it is difficult to identify patients with COVID-19 without a concomitant bacterial infection who can *было бы* safely stop taking antibiotics. However, recent clinical data show that procalcitonin can help assess the condition of these patients and reduce unnecessary use of antibiotics [18,19,25]. Therefore, we sought to determine the role of PCT and CRP in detecting bacterial co-infection in patients with COVID-19 pneumonia. Serum levels of CRP and PCT have a significant correlation with the severity of COVID-19 and can be used to as independent factors for predicting disease risk. Serum levels of CRP and PCT can effectively assess the severity of the disease and predict the outcome in patients with COVID-19. The study of the level of CRP in the blood serum is a mandatory laboratory study. Since the level of CRP correlates with the severity of the course, the prevalence of inflammatory infiltration and the prognosis for pneumonia. PCT is a well-known diagnostic marker of bacterial infection. [20, 28].

Purpose of the study. Study of serum procalcitonin levels to decide whether to start or discontinue antibiotic therapy, as well as to determine the progression of disease severity in COVID-19 patients.

Materials and methods: This study was a single-centre, retrospective cohort study. We included all patients with confirmed SARS-CoV-2 infection admitted to the Infectious diseases hospital from June 10 to September 12, 2020 in Bukhara. Clinical data was obtained from electronic medical records, including demographic data, exposure history, signs and symptoms, and laboratory data at admission. Upon admission to the inpatient emergency department, all patients were evaluated on the NEWS scale. The average score was 5.6 ± 1.4 . This made it possible to quickly sort out patients and send the most severe cases to the intensive care unit. All patients with COVID-19 included in this study were diagnosed in accordance with the guidelines for the diagnosis and treatment of pneumonia caused by a novel coronavirus infection. All patients were laboratory-confirmed to have SARS-CoV-2 infection (the result of real-time RT-PCR specific for SARS-CoV-2 was positive).

From June 10 to September 12, 2020, 120 patients were admitted to the Bukhara Regional Infectious Diseases Hospital. Patients were divided into severe cases (n=60) and moderate cases (n=60). Of these, 12 (20.0%) patients were admitted to the intensive care unit. The median age was 53 years, 120 patient and 96 (8.0%) of the 120 patients were male. The average time from the onset of symptoms to hospitalization was 2-3 days, and the average time to the diagnosis of a serious illness was 3-4 days.

A general blood test with determination of the number of white blood cells (WBC), lymphocytes (LYM), mononuclear cells (MONO), and neutrophils (NEU) was performed on blood samples. Blood biochemistry parameters: aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), glucose (GLU), urea, creatinine, and C-reactive protein (CRP) were measured using the MINDRAY BC – 30 automatics biochemical analyzer (China). The concentration OF PKT was determined using the ELISA method using reagent kits for enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay OF PKT CONCENTRATION in blood plasma PKT-ELISA-BEST. In patients with moderate and severe forms, the study was performed on the 2nd day of admission, the 3rd and 5th days of treatment. The upper limit of the norm was assumed to be the concentration of 0.05 ng/ml. The obtained data were compared with the recommendations for clinical interpretation of the results of determining the level of PCT in blood serum: 0.1-0.25 ng/ml – the probability of bacterial infection is very low; 0.25–0.5 ng/ml-local bacterial infection is possible; 0.5-2.0 ng/ml – high

probability of bacterial infection, systemic bacterial infection is possible; 2.0–10.0 ng/ml – high probability of systemic bacterial infection, possible severe sepsis; >10.0 ng/ml – high probability of severe sepsis[21, 23, 24].

Results. When studying the clinical picture, it was found that the most frequent symptom at admission was fever, detected in 115 patients, followed by respiratory symptoms, such as cough – in 92, sputum – in 25, shortness of breath – in 66, sore throat – in 75, hemoptysis – in 2 patients.

The most common gastrointestinal symptoms in patients with COVID-19 were: anorexia in 108, diarrhea in 16, nausea in 18, vomiting in 12, abdominal pain in 10 patients.

Neurological symptoms included headache in 105 patients, fatigue in 104 patients, dizziness in 37 patients, loss of taste in 35 patients, loss of smell in 38 patients, myalgia in 32 patients, confusion in 35 patients, convulsions in 4 patients (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Frequency of symptoms covidin covid-19 patients (%)

Ophthalmic manifestations were also recorded, such as conjunctivitis-in 48 patients, lacrimation – in 12 patients.

Based on the results of examination of 120 patients, it was found that 25 patients (20.8%) had skin manifestations. In 18 (20.8%) patients, they appeared simultaneously with the manifestation of other symptoms, in 7 (28%) patients-after hospitalization. Skin manifestations included angiitis in 10 patients, erythematous rash in 7 patients, widespread urticaria in 5 patients, and vesicles and papulosquamous rashes in 3 patients (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Specific weight of elements among skin manifestations in patients with covid-19 (%)

According to the results of laboratory data, it was found that 40 patients (33.3%) had leukopenia, 56 patients (46.7%) had leukocytosis; 88 patients (73.3%) had lymphocytopenia, and 24 patients (15.0%) had an increase in the number of lymphocytes.

Platelet counts and coagulation parameters were analyzed in the present study. Of the 120 patients included in the study, thrombocytopenia was detected in 23 (24.22%), thrombocytosis - in 18 (15.0%).

In 64 (53.3%) of 120 observed patients, the PCT content was 0.05-0.1 ng/ml, in 46 (38.3%) patients - 0.1-2.0 ng/ml, in 10 (8.4%) - more than 2.0 ng/ml (figure 3).

Figure 3.

These tests were obtained within the first 48-72 hours after the onset of the disease. And based on the content of PCT in the blood serum, they were conditionally divided into 3 groups. Further tests were repeated on the 3rd and 5th days, and in severe patients, the level of subcutaneous fat was also studied on the 7th day of treatment. Patients with a PCT level of more than 0.1 ng/ml were considered co-infected and were recommended for treatment with antibiotics (a combined drug of amoxicillin and clavulanic acid, cephalosporins of 2-3 generations), severe patients with meropenem and respiratory fluoroquinolones (levofloxacin). The effectiveness of treatment was assessed as insufficient if after 3 days of treatment there was no decrease in the level of PCT in the blood serum by 50%. In such cases, it can be assumed that the treatment does not give the expected effect. Therefore, it is necessary to change the tactics of antibacterial therapy. If the level of PCT decreases, it will mean that the treatment gave the expected result. As soon as there is a decrease in the number of PCT by about 80-90% from the peak level, it is recommended to stop antibacterial therapy. The results of the study showed that in 46 (71.9%) patients of the first group under observation, there was a significant decrease in the level of PCT, which did not differ from the norm, in 8 (12.5%) patients, the content of PCT remained unchanged. While 10 (15.6%) patients had an increase in the level of PCT in the blood serum and were prescribed antibacterial therapy.

Figure 4.

In 38 (82.6%) patients of group 2 who received antibacterial drugs, as in cases of co-infection, the content of PCT decreased by 50%, and in 8 (17.4%) patients, the level of PCT remained significantly high. Only 3 (30%) patients out of 10 seriously ill patients showed a positive result. When there was no decrease in the level of PCT on the 3rd day of treatment against the background of antibacterial therapy, another combination of antibacterial drugs was prescribed for the treatment of these patients.

Figure 5.

The data of our study, obtained on the 5th day of treatment, showed that according to the results of the first stage, the level of PCT significantly decreased and normalized in 18 patients of group 1. In 6 (13%) patients of group 2, the PCT level remained significantly high and continued treatment with antibacterial drugs. In 2 (20%) patients of group 3, despite the introduction of antibacterial drugs, the PCT level remained high, and the disease ended fatally.

Conclusion:

1. Procalcitonin is a biomarker for assessing the risk of bacterial infection and disease progression.
2. Procalcitonin levels can serve as biomarkers of bacterial infection joining COVID-19 and determine the timely administration of antibacterial drugs and the duration of the course of antibacterial therapy.
3. A decrease in the level of PCT by 80-90% from the peak level is one of the markers for stopping antibacterial therapy.

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For citation: Ergashov M.M. Clinical usefulness of procalcitonin in antibiotic decision-making during SARS-COV-2 infection // *Bulletin of Fundamental and Clinic Medicine*. – 2025. – № 6(20). – P. 1270–1275. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18001828>